

Designing Speaking Materials

Sinjabova Rusana Ruslanovna
e-mail: rusanagrey@gmail.com

PhD, associate professor of the Department of Economics and Socio-humanitarian Disciplines,
Almalyk Branch of NUST «MISIS», Almalyk 110100, Uzbekistan

Abstract. The article is about the problem of improving the efficiency of teaching oral speech in foreign language lessons, which is directly related to the problem of designing speaking materials. In this respect, the paper is devoted to present the main criteria which should be taken into consideration when designing speaking materials.

Key words: criteria, speaking, language, teacher, students, improvement, intermediate, learning, progress.

1 Introduction

Speaking is a crucial part of second language learning and teaching. Today's world requires that the goal of teaching speaking should improve students' communicative skills, because, only in that way, students can express themselves and learn how to follow the social and cultural rules appropriate in each communicative circumstance. The goal of teaching speaking skills is communicative efficiency. Learners should be able to make themselves understood, using their current proficiency to the fullest. They should try to avoid confusion in the message due to faulty pronunciation, grammar, or vocabulary, and to observe the social and cultural rules that apply in each communication situation. Making students speak is neither an easy nor a fast process. Teachers must be aware of some special techniques that will help to achieve the purpose. Speaking is an essential and inseparable part of a foreign learning and teaching. In past it was undervalued, and teachers taught speaking only through repetition of words, memorizing the dialogues, texts, verses and so on. Today the attitude to speaking has been changed.

2 Methods

Now, by teaching speaking we suppose producing the English speech sounds, using a word and sentence stress, selecting appropriate words and sentences to build an effective speech, organizing thoughts and, mainly, using the language as a means of communication. As we see, teaching speaking is not an easy deal, requiring definite knowledge and abilities. In other words, teachers of the English language need to be well versed in teaching oral skill and, as a consequence, at designing speaking materials in teaching English that is too complicated process.

It is especially actual issue nowadays, when most of teachers use only course books in teaching English speaking which are too complicated and boring. As Brian Tomlinson (2008) reports: "There is evidence that what teachers and learners actually do in the classroom is determined principally by what the course book tells them to do". As the result, many pupils and students find it difficult to respond if the teacher asks them to say something in the English language. It occurs because they have insufficient knowledge on a topic that they have to speak about and, consequently, they do not feel themselves confident in a classroom.

Thus, the process of designing speaking materials in teaching English is based on many various principles which are chosen by teachers according to their point of view. For instance, some famous linguists including Jack C Richards (2001) and Richard Schmidt (1990) consider that the main principles of designing speaking materials are principles of Communicative language teaching which are as follows:

- integrating language skills
- Accuracy and fluency
- Practicing the language
- Students creativity
- Authentic and meaningful communication

Similarly, Penny Ur (1996) sets such principles of designing speaking samples as:

- The use of time for talking
- Simplicity
- Minimal preparation
- Maximum interaction
- Interest
- Repetition
- Thinking skills

However, there are many other principles which teachers can take into consideration while designing speaking materials for teaching English. On the other hand, how to reveal which of them are the most effective in teaching English? It is a difficult question. In order to find answer on this question it is necessary to search what speaking samples are the most interesting and funny from learners' point of view. Thus, according to the survey, most of learners responded that the most interesting speaking they have ever had or that they would like to have during the English lesson are role-plays, presentations, picture descriptions, interviews and conversations.

Thus, role- plays may be given on various topics. Another plus is that all learners not depending on gender may actively participate in them. The same is with presentations. Moreover, both role- plays and presentations are devoted to development of learners' creativity and thinking skills as well. On the contrary, interviews and conversations reflect real needs of the learned language, while pictures help to develop both creativity and imagination. In general, all given speaking samples allow developing language accuracy and fluency.

3 Conclusion

To conclude, if we analyze them we shall detect that the given speaking samples are build on various types of interaction, maximum talk, students' creativity, thinking skills, various learning styles and needs which may function as effective principles at designing speaking materials in teaching English. Certainly, the level of learners also should be taken into account. Speaking materials should have special characteristics in order to help learners to improve their speaking abilities and self-confidence.

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